

Raw percentages 2-way ANOVA						Difference between raw and normalized data ?	Normalized to 4T1 D7 mean 2-way ANOVA					
Tukey's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff. percentage point	95% CI of diff.	Significant?	*	Adjusted P Value		Tukey's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff. norm. ratios	95% CI of diff.	Significant?	*	Adjusted P Value
4T1							4T1					
PDGFRa							PDGFRa					
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	29.72	20,23 to 39,22	Yes	****	<0,0001		4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	0.65	0,4848 to 0,8072	Yes	****	<0,0001
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	30.85	21,35 to 40,34	Yes	****	<0,0001		4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	0.63	0,4673 to 0,7897	Yes	****	<0,0001
4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	1.12	-8,047 to 10,29	No	ns	0.9552		4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	-0.02	-0,1732 to 0,1382	No	ns	0.9622
PDGFRb							PDGFRb					
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	9.55	0,05991 to 19,05	Yes	*	0.0482		4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	0.20	0,04247 to 0,3649	Yes	**	0.0088
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	10.50	1,011 to 20,00	Yes	*	0.0259		4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	0.23	0,06594 to 0,3883	Yes	**	0.0029
4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	0.95	-8,219 to 10,12	No	ns	0.9677		4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	0.02	-0,1323 to 0,1792	No	ns	0.9331
Podoplanin							Podoplanin					
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	17.27	7,772 to 26,76	Yes	****	<0,0001		4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	0.34	0,1831 to 0,5055	Yes	****	<0,0001
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	23.78	14,29 to 33,27	Yes	****	<0,0001		4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	0.44	0,2836 to 0,6059	Yes	****	<0,0001
4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	6.52	-2,656 to 15,69	No	ns	0.2175		4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	0.10	-0,05530 to 0,2562	No	ns	0.2839
FAPa							FAPa					
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	-8.43	-17,92 to 1,067	No	ns	0.0936	yes	4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	-0.21	-0,3662 to -0,04386	Yes	**	0.0082
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	-15.40	-24,89 to -5,905	Yes	***	0.0005		4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	-0.36	-0,5261 to -0,2037	Yes	****	<0,0001
4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	-6.97	-16,14 to 2,199	No	ns	0.1748	yes	4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	-0.16	-0,3156 to -0,004108	Yes	*	0.0427
aSMA							aSMA					
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	9.11	-0,3859 to 18,60	No	ns	0.0632	yes	4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	0.36	0,1987 to 0,5210	Yes	****	<0,0001
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	11.10	1,603 to 20,59	Yes	*	0.0171		4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	0.42	0,2622 to 0,5846	Yes	****	<0,0001
4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	1.99	-7,182 to 11,16	No	ns	0.8664		4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	0.06	-0,09214 to 0,2193	No	ns	0.6022
CD26							CD26					
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	-8.33	-17,82 to 1,166	No	ns	0.0989	yes	4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 14	-0.20	-0,3607 to -0,03828	Yes	*	0.0106
4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	-9.24	-18,73 to 0,2539	No	ns	0.0584	yes	4T1Day 7 vs. 4T1day 21	-0.24	-0,4018 to -0,07943	Yes	**	0.0014
4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	-0.91	-10,08 to 8,258	No	ns	0.9702		4T1day 14 vs. 4T1day 21	-0.04	-0,1969 to 0,1146	No	ns	0.8084
4T07							4T07					
PDGFRa							PDGFRa					
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	12.25	2,537 to 21,97	Yes	**	0.009		4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	0.25	0,02512 to 0,4834	Yes	*	0.0254
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	5.10	-5,840 to 16,03	No	ns	0.5167		4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	0.10	-0,1592 to 0,3565	No	ns	0.6401
4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	-7.16	-18,38 to 4,061	No	ns	0.2912		4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	-0.16	-0,4201 to 0,1090	No	ns	0.3504
PDGFRb							PDGFRb					
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	17.08	7,361 to 26,79	Yes	***	0.0001		4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	0.31	0,08233 to 0,5406	Yes	**	0.0043
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	15.41	4,473 to 26,34	Yes	**	0.0029		4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	0.31	0,04906 to 0,5648	Yes	*	0.0148
4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	-1.67	-12,89 to 9,550	No	ns	0.9346		4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	0.00	-0,2691 to 0,2600	No	ns	0.9991
Podoplanin							Podoplanin					
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	14.38	4,664 to 24,10	Yes	**	0.0016		4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	0.26	0,02872 to 0,4869	Yes	*	0.0229
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	20.38	9,446 to 31,32	Yes	****	<0,0001		4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	0.38	0,1239 to 0,6396	Yes	**	0.0016
4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	6.00	-5,218 to 17,22	No	ns	0.4194		4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	0.12	-0,1407 to 0,3884	No	ns	0.5133
FAP							FAP					
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	-10.50	-20,22 to -0,7858	Yes	*	0.0305	yes	4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	-0.22	-0,4513 to 0,006963	No	ns	0.0596
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	-4.48	-15,42 to 6,452	No	ns	0.5994		4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	-0.13	-0,3872 to 0,1285	No	ns	0.4655
4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	6.02	-5,201 to 17,24	No	ns	0.4173		4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	0.09	-0,1717 to 0,3574	No	ns	0.6872
aSMA							aSMA					
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	10.36	0,6476 to 20,08	Yes	*	0.0334		4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	0.34	0,1111 to 0,5694	Yes	**	0.0016
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	11.80	0,8686 to 22,74	Yes	*	0.0308		4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	0.42	0,1609 to 0,6766	Yes	***	0.0005
4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	1.44	-9,779 to 12,66	No	ns	0.9509		4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	0.08	-0,1860 to 0,3431	No	ns	0.7643
CD26							CD26					
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	4.44	-5,279 to 14,15	No	ns	0.5302		4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 14	0.13	-0,09785 to 0,3604	No	ns	0.3693
4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	18.60	7,668 to 29,54	Yes	***	0.0002		4T07 day 7 vs. 4T07 day 21	0.36	0,09721 to 0,6129	Yes	**	0.0037
4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	14.17	2,946 to 25,38	Yes	**	0.0089	yes	4T07 day 14 vs. 4T07 day 21	0.22	-0,04075 to 0,4884	No	ns	0.1158

